

Visual symbolism and artistic expressions in Tsikor Clan's Chieftaincy Rites in Amedzofe

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Abstract: The chieftaincy institutions in Ghana are deeply embedded in cultural traditions and visual symbolism, yet certain localized practices remain underexplored. This study investigates and discusses the indigenous artistic expressions and symbolic visual elements embedded in the chieftaincy installation rites of the Tsikor clan in Amedzofe in the Avatime Traditional Area. The research addresses a significant academic gap such as the lack of documentation and scholarly attention given to the cultural performances, visual art forms, aesthetics and the unique ritual nature of chief installation procedure in the Tsikor clan by highlighting its visual and performing arts to gain deeper understanding. Employing a qualitative research approach, the study utilized descriptive and an Auto-ethnographic Turn in Design to explore lived experiences and meanings. Data were collected through participant observation using purposive sampling for interviews with six individuals closely connected to the ritual practices. The data were analyzed using narrative and interpretive phenomenological analysis, alongside thematic analysis to uncover recurring cultural and artistic themes. Findings reveal the uniqueness of the installation rites which are rich with symbolic attire, indigenous regalia, and artistic performances that encapsulate the values, identity, and continuity of the Tsikor clan. The study recommends the promotion and the outdoor of the cultural heritages involved in the chiefs' installation procedures of the Tsikor Clan.

Keywords: Chieftaincy, Clan, *Dzikle*, Indigenous, Rituals, Traditional

1. Introduction

Ghana Broadcasting Corporation (2021) indicated that Avatime is the capital of the Avatime Area and it is situated on the eastern side of the Akuapem-Togo ranges. This escarpment is recognized as one of the highest human settlements in Ghana above sea level. Avatime traditional area harbours eight communities under hierarchical chieftaincy system. These include Amedzofe, Biakpa, Dzogbefeme, Fume, Gbadzeme, New Dзокpe, Old Dзокpe and Vane being the administrative capital.

Figure 1. The map and location the Avatime Area (Source: Buglass, n. d.)

The people of Avatime practice and engage in farming as their main occupation. This agricultural activity yields large quantities of crops, especially rice despite the challenging mountainous terrain in the area (Agbanyo, 2012). Bormann (2015) further stated that the Amu Festival is a community-wide celebration centred on the cultivation and harvesting of brown rice (amu), a staple crop that holds both economic and symbolic significance for the Avatime. The festival serves not only as a thanksgiving ritual for a successful harvest but also as a medium for reinforcing social cohesion, cultural identity, and indigenous knowledge systems related to agriculture. Through ritual performances, communal feasting, and traditional displays, the Amu Festival affirms the central role of rice in the socio-cultural life of the Avatime people (Bormann, 2015). Avatime populace exhibit their culture and its values, they are proud of the rich culture that spectacularly holds hidden artistic elements during their chieftaincy installations in each of their indigenous communities (Dedume, 2015). Scholars agree that among the Avatime people, the transition of girls into womanhood is marked through sacred initiation rituals known as *kusakɔ kɔ*, which are supported by local chiefs under the authority of the Paramount Chiefs referred to as "Osie" in Vane (Brydon, 1981; Defina, 2012; Dedume, 2015; Lapushkina, 2020). These ceremonies include rituals with valuable educational, moral and cultural values. Other leadership structures in the Avatime Traditional Area which include several notable positions in addition to the village Chiefs are called *Okusie* (meaning chiefs), *Tsiamewo* (referred to as linguists) who are spokespersons and or advisors, *Shefiawo* (youth chiefs who organizes the youth), *Mankrado* (caretaker when chief is absent and presides over all traditional ritual performances) who assist in local governance (101 Last Tribes, n.d.). Women in Avatime society also hold the title *Odze Okusie*, translating to "woman chief." (Brydon, 1996). Execution of duties by these leadership structures reveal the administrative and cultural preservation of the Avatime people.

Awuah-Nyamekye (2009) stated that within the Akan society, the process of enstoolment is deeply rooted in religious practices, involving divination, prayers and sacrifices. These rituals are integral to the selection and installation of a chief. Adjei (2018) stated that the stool rituals in Anfoega-Ewe signify and symbolize the authority of the chief and it is embodied in the soul of the community. It ensures adequate nourishment and empowerment of the youth, stabilizing the position of the chief and ensuring the well-being of the populace. Adjei (2018: 36) again emphasized that "sacrificial offerings are made to revitalize the sacred stool by conducting animal sacrifices". "The blood of the slaughtered animal is used to anoint the stool, as blood is considered a symbol of life and precious gift to the supernatural entities" (Adjei, 2018: 35). "The ancestral stools, believed to embody the spirits of past rulers, are ritually purified to sanctify the spiritual space before the new chief assumes office" (Omenyo, 2011, p. 6). It cleanses any spiritual impurities and connects the new leader with the ancestors and for protection. In confinement and training of a chief-elect among the Dagombas, the new chief undergoes rituals to understand customs, history and values to maintain tradition and how to lead effectively. Omenyo (2011) insisted that the chief-elect is secluded and tutored on royal duties, lineage history and traditional customs to ensure readiness for leadership. In the Anlo state, rituals typically involve the use of specific herbs and

libations, performed by designated ritual specialists. It serves to invoke the blessings of the ancestors, ensuring the new leader's reign is divinely guided and protected (Adotey, 2018). After this, the chief is allowed to ceremoniously sit on the stool to let spirits of predecessors connect with him and affirm continuity of leadership. Among the Ga community, a purification ceremony is symbolically conducted at dawn. Ammah (1966) claims that it involves the use of sacred water, herbs, and the recitation of ancestral praises. More often than not, this ritual does not only cleanse the stool but also reaffirms the chief's commitment to uphold the values and traditions of the Ga people. This practice proves the spiritual and authority value of the chief upon sitting on the stool called the *dzase* which is believed to have contained the spirits of former chiefs and embodies the collective identity of the clan.

However, as an identified research gap, the distinctive and unique cultural performances, visual art forms, aesthetic and the unique ritual nature of chiefs' installation procedure in the Tsikor clan in Amedzofe which highlight visual and performing arts has not been scholarly researched and documented. This study therefore highlights the need for its scholarly attention. These also include purifications, incantations, oral traditions, exhibition of costumes, preservation of culture, shaping of moral values and spiritual protections. However, as indicated by Museums and Monuments Board (2014), there was a collaboration with Presbyterian University College to hold a memorial lecture to honour the study of Ewe language and further promoted the intertwining of art and culture in the region. The National Commission on Culture has consistently promoted the integration of art into cultural expressions across Ghana in 2011 primarily to highlight the role of art in cultural identity and heritage. These served as a platform to showcase the artistic and cultural narratives of various Ghanaian communities including those from Volta region. The Centre for National Culture in Volta Region in 2024 hosted the Volta Regional Arts and Culture Festival to showcase a variety of artistic performances, crafts and cultural exhibitions to show the significance of art in the cultural fabric of the Volta communities (Centre for National Culture-Volta Region, 2024). Unknowingly, the Tsikor clan chief installations involve the exhibition of cultural performances, visual art forms, aesthetic and rituals, sanctimonious nature of chief installation procedures and both visual and performing arts that need deeper understanding also need to be recognized. This study therefore seeks to reveal the artistic visual arts and a variety of cultural values and rituals as part of the customs and traditions that requires scholarly attention from the Tsikor Clan in the Avatime Traditional Area.

Figure 2: A view of Amedzofe and its enclave (source: Penuku, 2023)

2. Literature review

2.1. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical foundation underpinning this study which tends to reveal the artistic values harboured in the traditional and ritual performances during leadership installations in Tsikor clan is the Theory of Functionalism propounded by Durkheim (Durkheim, 1995). From a Durkheimian functionalist perspective, the artistic values embedded in the Tsikor clan's leadership installation rituals serve to reaffirm communal values, reinforce social

solidarity, and legitimize the newly installed leaders within the group. Contemporary studies in Ghana confirm and expand this functionalist perspective. For example, Azaglo et al. (2024) demonstrate that the aesthetic elements in Tagbayiyi ritual performances of the Fiasidi tradition embody cultural identity, reinforce communal values, and integrate participants into collective experience. Similarly, Kilu and Sanda (2025) emphasize that creative arts in Ghanaian contexts are not merely expressive but function to transmit knowledge, social norms, and cultural meanings within communities. Micah et al. (2022) further illustrate that traditional masquerade performances among the Effutu are functional mechanisms for transmitting beliefs, reinforcing identity, and regulating social behavior.

Together, these studies align with Durkheimian functionalism, showing that artistic elements in leadership installations and ritual performances, such as those observed in the Tsikor clan, are integral to maintaining social order, affirming shared values, and sustaining cultural continuity. These are chieftaincy rituals, including artistic expressions during installations that function to unite the people, reinforce hierarchy, and preserve culture. Also, International Journal of Home Economics (2022) propelled the symbolic interactionism theory. This theory focuses on how people create meaning through their interactions using symbols especially in chieftaincy installations, elements like stools, regalia, cloths, drums, and linguist staff are not just objects but symbols of authority, lineage, and power. In terms of costumes and regalia, Navei (2024) explains how Safo-Ankama and Sawyerr (2023) touched on the Asafo battle costumes, which project and protect the wearer, come in different types such as; fugu (smocks), tapestries, plain white, blue-red, and yellow fabrics, depending on their source of allegiance or objects of benevolence. Asante (2003) mentioned the Afrocentric Theory. It highlights how rituals, symbols, and artistic traditions in chieftaincy reflect African spirituality, aesthetics, and governance systems.

2.2. Art in Sacred Performances in Communities

Many scholars argue that cultural forms, including art, function as repositories of collective and cultural memory, encoding shared myths and symbols and enabling a dialogue between past and present (Assmann & Assmann, 2011). This perspective underscores how aesthetic practices serve as critical means for communities to preserve their heritage while articulating collective identity. Art forms such as music, costumes, body arts and incantations are all activities expressed to spell out cultural narratives and cultural values. Art embedded within ritual practices functions as a vital medium through which cultural memory, symbols, and shared meanings are preserved and transmitted across generations, thereby sustaining communal identity and continuity. Cultural memory theorists argue that symbolic forms such as ritual performances, visual motifs, and artistic enactments provide structured frameworks for recalling and reproducing collective traditions over time (Assmann, 2011). Similarly, ritual scholars emphasize that symbols enacted through ritual and performance reinforce social values and communal cohesion, ensuring the persistence of tradition within society (Turner, 1983). From an aesthetic perspective, art further mediates cultural memory by embodying sensory and symbolic cues that enable communities to recall and sustain shared histories and identities (Mortu, 2024). Nyarko and Yorke (2024, as cited in Azaglo et al., 2024) explain that festivals play a vital role in the cultural heritage of a group of people and serve as a means of showcasing rich traditions. In addition, the Gologo festival of the people of Tongo employs artefacts including bows and arrows, horns (metallic dangles worn around the ankle and used as musical instruments during dancing), and a leather belt worn by the war dancers (Ayensu et al., 2020).

All these traditional cultural performances reveal artistic values we adore in our communities. Adjepong and Obeng (2018) also emphasized that performing arts comprise music, dance, and drama which normally go on during festival celebrations, funeral rites, durbars, marriage, and naming ceremonies to entertain people. Visual arts are central to the celebration of the Aboakyer Festival, serving not only aesthetic purposes but also fulfilling functional and economic roles that reinforce the socio-cultural identity of the Effutu community (Impraim-Swanzy, Arthur & Asante, 2019). The visual arts used in the Aboakyer festival are 'art for art's sake...functional

and encompass all the characteristics associated with African arts (Swanzy-Impraim 2019). The essence of arts in cultural festivities is empirically supported that “it is the performing arts which define and enhance the power of rulers in the public domain” (Ampene, 2021: 525). This explored the role of performing arts in Asante royal ceremonies, asserting that these arts are essential in legitimating and projecting the power of rulers. Christopher (2013: 10) in his coined concept during a case study on the Asogli Yam festival explained that, “performing art forms provide essential knowledge to visitors and community members who attend traditional festivals”. Music, dance and drama instrumentally educate audiences about cultural values and traditions. Navei (2024) agreed that Kvkɔrɔ Festival holds artistic expressions including performances and rituals that contribute to the preservation of cultural heritage and promote communal values. The significance of arts in the Ghanaian cultural performances in another vein is mentioned by Arhin et al. (2024) that creative artists are packaging beverages, using waste materials uniquely, traditional festivals, traditional music and traditional entertainment creatively needing government’s support to scale it for socio-economic impact. In the cultural dimensions of the Homowo festival celebrated by the Ga community.

Nortey (2009: 5) revealed that it involves a great deal of arts with environmental, performing, body and verbal arts playing predominant roles in its celebration. In keeping memories of events for future generations, Seble (2023) opined that his work captures moments of communion with the sacred, aiming to glorify Togolese culture and preserve its rich heritage through his photography as an art component. He finalized that his art immortalizes traditional rites with spiritual and cultural importance.

3. Research methodology

This study explored the artistic elements in the Tsikor community’s indigenous arts and ritual practices during their chief installations. It primarily pivoted purely with a qualitative approach with a combination of descriptive, visual and auto-ethnographic turn in design and case study components for an in-depth analysis of specific artistic and ritual practices within the community. Ellis et al. (2011) claimed that autoethnography involves the researcher reflecting on their personal experiences to gain insights into cultural phenomena.

The population for this study included one of the researchers, a native of the community, who served as both a participant and co-investigator, offering personal narratives through auto-ethnographic methods. Purposive sampling was used to select participants made up of a traditional priest and four elders from the community and an insider-researcher summing up to a total sample size of six (6). Patton (2015) agrees that using small purposive samples in qualitative research focuses on information-rich cases and not statistical generalizations. The study area took place within and among the Tsikor clan within the larger community in Vane. Data was collected using photographs, semi-structured interviews with open-ended questions on symbolism, techniques, and meanings of artworks and rituals, the participant observation method which provided a trustworthy and authentic recording. These included the use of symbols and performance elements. Creswell and Creswell (2018) highlighted the value of triangulating data sources to enhance credibility and depth of research findings by integrating various qualitative methods such as interviews, observations and visual materials to gain comprehensive understanding of community dynamics. This makes way for adequate validity for data analysis since it provides results with a variety of data collection methods. Pink (2013) also advocates for the use of photography in ethnographic research and argues that photographs can serve as a medium to explore and represent the experience and perspectives of research participants. Again, DeWalt and DeWalt (2011: 1) defined participant observation as “a method in which the researcher takes part in the daily activities, rituals, interactions, and events of a group of people as one of the means of learning the explicit and tacit aspects of their life routines”.

To focus on the detailed examination of personal lived experiences to understand meanings that are affiliated to art and sacred practices both narrative and interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) methods

were used as suggested by Smith et al. (2021) that it is ideal for studies that aim to explore subjective meanings from the participants points of view. Inductive thematic analysis method was used to organize, transcribe, analyze, and interpret the data collected as suggested by Braun and Clarke (2006) who claimed that the benefits of applying inductive thematic analysis in qualitative research is to generate sincere validity in the analysis due to its transparency and authenticity. Photographs were taken and interviews collected by the will of participants including the participant-researcher. Participants were not exploited during interviews and in findings. Identities of participants in the performances were censored. Cultural sensitivities and property rights of indigenous artworks were interacted with, with respect

4. Findings and discussion

4.1. Installation of Chiefs among the Tsikor Clan in Amedzofe

The installation of chiefs begins with the nomination of potential candidates from the royal family. This is done by the *Bakatsistiwa* (elders), *Ligboleoke* (stool father), *Bebikawa* (parents) and some selected personalities from the royal family *Axortorwa* (family heads). This group of people are referred to as *Okusiebedzudzuwa* (Kingmakers) of the clan or community.

4.2. Endorsement of a candidate

This process is characterized by a series of activities with various stages. It is noted that this process has no definite time nor duration since conditions at these stages may determine how quick or long it would take to the next stage. What is worth noting, also, that there are established criteria used by *Okusiebedzudzuwa* in endorsing the candidature of a nominee to become a chief. Srem-Sai (2021) emphasized that endorsing a candidate for enstoolment is the foundational step, stating that it provides the foundation on the basis of which the other processes will take place.

The first activity is the nomination of potential candidates from the royal family. Elders and family heads are given this mandate. As many nominees as possible are given out leading to the next stage where there is scaling down of the number of nominees through *Kutiatia* (selection) which is done by the *Okusiebedzudzuwa* of the clan using the established criteria. The process continues until a final consensus is reached by the *Okusiebedzudzuwa* where a single nominee stands out from the rest signifying his ability to satisfy all the qualities expected through the criteria. This aligns with how the republic of Ghana (1992) outlines, in the 1992 Constitution of Ghana and the Chieftaincy Act 2008 (Act 759), the procedures for chieftaincy succession. The article 277 of the constitution emphasizes that “a chief is someone who has been validly nominated, elected and installed” (Republic of Ghana, 1992: 152). However, in the situation where two nominees appear to be at par regarding the demands of the criteria, the *Bakatsitretrewa* (ancestors) and the *Babuwa* (gods) are consulted through special rites and rituals where libation is performed in the shrine and *Orbukae* (chief priest or the divine seer) performs a ritual to receive the message from the *Babuwa* to ascertain the most qualified nominee who will sit on the stool for them. Consultations are usually made before nominees are finally chosen just as Moses (n.d.) states that in the Dagbon traditional area, the selection of a new chief involves consulting soothsayers or diviners. Moses confirms that this practice dates back to the 17th century and later elders consulted soothsayers who unanimously selected the chief of Yamol-Karaga, a small village, as the new paramount chief as a replacement.

These practices do not happen in public, since the processes are considered sacred and spiritual hence made confidential and secured. They are therefore done with confidentiality. While all these are going on, other preparations of acquiring materials and personalities who would perform the necessary rites and rituals would be made in advance (S. K. Boateng, personal communication, April 12, 2025).

Based on the above, the *Okusiebedzudzuwa* would consider the atmosphere at the time to determine whether to inform the endorsed candidate about their intentions or not. Whichever way it takes, a day is set for the next process where the said candidate would be captured and confined.

4.3. The capture

Chieftaincy installation processes start with capturing in most Ghanaian communities. This serves many purposes. It symbolizes that the call to serve is not spiritual and not self-motivated. (S. K. Boateng, personal communication, March, 13 2025). Adanwomase (n. d.) ascertained that to avoid outright refusal, the elders secretly execute it unaware and begin confinement and rituals before the nominee gets the opportunity to decline. The Effutu State (n. d.) also emphasized that the selection and seizing of the candidate is done in secrecy to maintain the sanctity of the custom and avoid sabotage. The capture is a technical terminology used to describe the seizure of the candidate for confinement. This marks a legitimate criterion to be observed. This makes the installation an accepted one. Ababio (2023) claimed that the enstoolment processes should be guided by the act to ensure legitimacy and prevent disputes. As explained earlier, this process takes place either with or without the knowledge of the candidate through an anxious expedition as it happens “among the Akan of Ghana, particularly the Guan and Akan societies, it is customary for a chief nominee to be captured or seized unexpectedly, even if they are aware of their royal eligibility” (Ephirim-Donkor, 2025: 64).

Busia (1951) also describes the custom among the Ashanti where the chosen royal is seized unexpectedly, symbolizing that chieftaincy is not a personal ambition but a communal calling. It is done to prevent any refusal and to ensure the person accepts the responsibility. Either of them is performed by timing the candidate either in the open or an enclosed location where a special concoction made of a number of herbs and *ayilb* or *shilé* white clay in a calabash is poured on the head of the candidate. Adzei (2018) confirms that the use of ‘*danie*’-a mixture of water eggs, and herbs-as a purifying agent applied to the head, face, and arms of participants before entering the stool room maintains sanctity of the stool and the rituals performed therein. This signifies that the gods and the ancestors have laid their sacred and spiritual hands on him. Asamoah-Gyadu (2015) notes that the use of libation and other rituals during installations underscores the transformation of the candidate into a moral, political and religious leader of the community. After, *Asafo* (a group of young men and women) then rush in quickly to get hold of him before he thinks of running away. This explains the concept of ‘the capture’. In sum, amid singing of *Asafoe idzine* (war songs), clapping hands over the mouth is ecstasy, the candidate is carried over the neck along some principal streets of the town to announce the success of the expedition (W. K. Sewornu, personal communication, March 8, 2025).

4.4. Confinement

Confinement is a period during which a chief nominee is secluded before their official publicity and oath swearing. In the Effutu Traditional Area, the nominee is confined for seven days, culminating in a dawn procession to a sacred site for prayers before the oath swearing ceremony (Effutu State, n.d.)

For seven days, according to the customs and tradition, the candidate is confined in a room at a secluded location within the town, guarded by the *abu* (royal guards) who also carry errands night and day. He is taken through lessons by some selected *Okusiebedzudzuwa* on customs and tradition, beliefs, rules and regulations, moral standards of chiefs and leaders of the community, general attitudes which include self-discipline, truthfulness, fairness, decency and honesty, among many others. Asamoah-Gyedu (2015) discusses the confinement period often referred to as “quarantine” wherein the chief-elect is secluded for a prescribed duration and receives instructions on roles of chieftaincy and ancestral ceremonies required with rituals, sacrifices, oath-taking and spiritual fortifications. He is also visited by other clan chiefs in succession to show solidarity and to share their experiences with him. Confinement is a customary practice that is observed in the

Tsikor clan where the chief-elect undergoes a period of seclusion (W. K. Sewornu, personal communication, March 8, 2025).

4.5. Outdooring

A new chief is ceremoniously led out from his seclusion into the open where the community gathers. This physical outdooring signifies his appearance as a public figure and traditional leader. Ammah (2016, p. 225) portrayed outdooring as a ritual that “brings the leader out into the yard” to be recognized by the community, with libations and blessings that link him to both the ancestral and natural orders”. In another context, as some see outdooring as a ceremony for children freshly born, it is ceremoniously designed to unravel the identity for traditional leaders too. Tetteh (2016) also claimed that while focusing on the outdooring, dedication, and naming of an African child, same ritual mechanics such as public presentation, ritual cleansing, and the ceremonial bestowal of a name and identity are paradigmatic of rites of passage in Ghanaian culture, and by extension applied when a chief is installed. It is illustrated that during the outdooring ceremony the new chief is not simply announced but is ritually “reborn” into his role. The ceremonial acts and procession into the public sphere, the pouring of libations, the symbolic cleansing, and the bestowal of regalia work together to connect the chief with his lineage, the spiritual forces of the land, and the collective identity and future of his community (Odotei, 1989).

On the eighth day, a durbar of chiefs under the authority of the Paramount Chief (if available) and the entire community is held to formally present the groomed candidate to the community. This reflects similar concepts of the people of Akan who organize durbars for the installation of chiefs, kings, and queens, and their elders as Smithsonian Institution (1997) stated, and that, at the durbar chiefs and their elders appear in public procession amidst intensive drumming, singing and dancing. In the context of art, this concept reveals the types of costumes that are culturally and aesthetically adored by the people of the Tsikor community.

Figure 2a. *Dziklebiwa* in kente, costumes and body paintings with *dzikle* on their heads (Source: Fieldwork, 2024)

The *dziklebiwa* (young girls and maidens) are clad in rich *kugosaa* (kente cloths) and other native clothes with *dzikle* (loads of assorted fabrics, cosmetics, beads on their heads), adorned with beautiful body paintings. Jewelry items carried by maidens hold spiritual significance (Impraim-Swanzy and Arthur, 2019). It also shows the community’s wealth, status and cultural heritage.

The items are not merely decorative but are imbued with meanings that reflect the community’s values and besides “special beads like *nsie* and *ehuma* are used to signify affiliation with particular Asafo companies during festivals, highlighting the importance of these ornaments in denoting social identity” (Impraim-Swanzy, Arthur and Asante 2016).

This body art purposely provides beautification, spiritual protection and for medicinal gains. In procession, the *dziklebiwa* followed by Chiefs and Queens all dressed in their *bikusidome* (royal regalia) and the *Okusie* (candidate) adorned in white apparel with white woven scarfs round the head, a beautiful white native *Kente* cloth wrapped over the left shoulder with a suitable *Ahenemma* (native sandals), *Bakatsistiwa* and *Okusiebedzudzuwa* under colourful *Kalawewa* (royal umbrellas), with *Dzagbɔwa* (linguist staffs), *Ekusigbola* (royal stools), *Itsile* (mats) and *Kugapleka* (skins of white sheep and antelope). The use of the white sheep signifies peace and purity that is needed for the Tsikor territory and its citizens. Arthur et al. (2018) stresses that skins including those of sheep are used as a stool tops and floor mats during chieftaincy rituals and that they are merely decorative but serve as symbols of the chief's authority and sacredness of the chieftaincy institution. With melodious drumming, singing and dancing *eUu vidina* artistically exhibits the indigenous performing art by both men and women, young and old, filing through the principal streets to the durbar ground in a very colourful and orderly manner. "Following confinement, the chief elect is publicly introduced to the community in a ceremony that includes traditional music, drumming and dancing" (Adanwomase.com, n.d.). These mark the beginning of the *o'oenokububu* (outdooing) process where the entire community sees the candidate for the first time after confinement.

Figure 2b: *Dziklebiwa* are clad in rich traditional costumes and body paintings carrying *dzikle* on their heads (Source: Fieldwork, 2024)

4.6. Swearing of Royal Oath

At the durbar, everyone sits in expectation of witnessing an enstoolment event. Chiefs, Queens and elders sit according to their ranks as always. The *ogbedoe* (chief orator) is invited to perform *igbedodole* (oral art/incantations/ libation) for the commencement of the last process of installation of the new chief. This serves as an oral art as a form of performing art. (W. K. Sewornu, personal communication, March 17, 2025).

Figure 3: *Ogbedoe* pouring libation with *deha* (Source: Fieldwork, 2024)

On this occasion, an oath is sworn. Swearing an oath during the enstoolment of chiefs and queens is a mandatory ritual that initiates their authority and binds them to their both spiritual and duty to serve as expected by the community. Addo (2004) opined that the importance of oath-swearing is that it serves as a reference point for deskinnment or destoolment of a chief should he breach the injunction or taboos. It also serves as a source of true and brave commitment. Tsekpoe (2019) confirms that the practice of oath taking during enstoolment is not attributed to a single individual but it is a longstanding tradition embedded in Ghanaian customary law. It has been preserved and passed down through generations by traditional authorities and elders within various ethnic groups. Worth noting, is the fact that despite all the above activities the candidate remains 'ordinary' until the oath is administered while the necessary rites are performed in the full glare of the people in the community. Tsekpoe (2019: 10) emphasized this that "until a new leader swears the traditional oath, he is not considered as fully installed.

Another essential stage is marked by the pouring of libation. Libation is clearly defined as a means of connecting to spiritual gods or God through an incantation with a ceremonial act of pouring of either water or a drink. For the benefit of spiritual communication and ancestral veneration, Nehusi (2015) defines libation as a ritual of heritage within the African Circle of Life, marking transformations through different stages in the human journey. It is a means of honouring ancestors and deities, acknowledging their role in the lives of the living. Another essence of pouring libation is for cultural identity and continuity. This is clearly claimed by Felix (2024) that the act of pouring libation reinforces cultural identity and continuity, serving as a reminder of the community's traditions. "In Ga society, libation is performed to appeal to the Supreme Being through gods and ancestors, as a direct access to the Supreme Being is mediated by these entities" (Gyima (n.d: 1)

At this stage amongst the Tsikor clan, *deha* (palm wine) or *akpeteshie* (local gin dry gin or schnapps) are used to invite the *ogbedoe* (the orator) to invoke the divine spirits and presence of the deities, ancestors, gods and the *Ayaa* (Supreme God) to grant the community a successful occasion through pouring libation. Gyimah (n.d.) believes that the Supreme Being, *Ataa Naa Nyongmo*, is the creator of the universe so the Ga people appeal to God through intermediaries (gods) and ancestors via the act of pouring libation. This practice serves as maintaining harmony between the physical and spiritual realms. On one hand, and for His blessings, guidance, protection and divine wisdom for the new chief in the discharge of his mandate. This is also marked by the declaration of his strong desire to accept the duty and responsibility being placed on him by the elders and Kingmakers of his community. It is therefore, expressed by a statement or promise which is strengthened or affirmed by such a pledge. The candidate is given *kitampamia* (a sacred sword) in the middle of the durbar ground. *Okusieka* (His royal father) ceremoniously, faces him to receive the oath from the prospective chief to the stool father and the paramount chief (if alive).

The candidate raises *kitampamia* (the sword) points it to the royal father and orally presents his statement of affirmation as Asante (1975) also puts it that "the subordinator or chief-elect now stands erect and proceeds to swear the oath of allegiance, pointing the sword at the superior chief" (p. 16) among the Akans. The sacred sword is handed over to his royal father who will also affirm his support and loyalty to the candidate on behalf of the deities, ancestors, gods of the land and *Ayaa*. "Swords serve critical roles in ritual events such as a paramount chief's enstoolment. The ruler-elect grasps a specific sword to take the oath of office" (Cole, 2014, p. 47). This rite is welcomed with loud shouts of ecstasy followed by exciting singing, drumming and dancing by the community.

Figure 3. The candidate raises the *kitampamia*, points it to the royal father and orally presents his statement of affirmation

(Source: Fieldwork, 2024)

4.7. Consummation

In another event a white ram is slaughtered right in front of the candidate by *ogayee* (the chief butcher) where the blood of the ram is allowed to spill onto the ground. The slaughtered ram is raised up and passed over the candidate's head in a circular motion for three consecutive times while some invocations are made. This act is explained by Adjei (2018) that "the ritual of sacrifice (dzododo) is performed to revivify the sacred stool with animal blood through animal sacrifice in which the blood of the slaughtered (ram) is used to besmear the sacred stool" (p. 36). The fur of the ram is plucked and placed on the candidate's head with pronouncements asking for good health, long life, divine wisdom, prosperity among others for the candidate. The significance of this is to seek purity, goodwill and to be as gray as white fur of the lamb (Ogayee, personal communication, April 15, 2025). The final rite involves the placing of the right foot into the blood of the ram three times in succession by the chief priest. This signifies the fusion of energy and positivity to proceed with growth and good intentions for the community. In addition, the chief priest dips his fingers into the blood of the ram and places it on the candidate's tongue three times in succession which establishes the acceptance of the candidate by the deities, ancestors, the gods and *Ayaa*.

This is the stage where the candidate is finally and officially declared as a recognized chief for the clan. What follows next includes cultural drumming, singing and dancing by the various cultural groups from the community (High Priest, personal communication, April 15, 2025). Slaughtering a ram carries more specific significance in Ghanaian communities. "Oratory in Akan society is not just about eloquence but also about the strategic use of language to navigate complex social and political landscapes. It serves the dignity of the chief and the people in addressing issues". (Yankah, 1995: 122). Additionally, "this act signals the sealing of an oath by the chief to serve the people and uphold traditions, with the sheep serving as a sacred witness" (Opoku, 1978: 93). In sum, Afriyie (2020: 136), opined that "the sheep slaughtered upon the Ofori Kuma stool during the Odwira festival symbolizes the cleansing of the state and the renewal of oaths between divisional chiefs and the paramount chief".

Figure 4a: A white ram is slaughtered right in front of the candidate by the *ogayee* where the blood of the ram is allowed to spill onto the ground. (Source: Fieldwork, 2024)

Figure 4b: The slaughtered ram is raised up and passed over the candidate's head thrice (Source: Fieldwork, 2024)

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study impetrated to unmask the indigenous artistic visual arts and a variety of cultural values and rituals as part of the customs and traditions that requires scholarly attention in the Tsikor Clan in the Avatime Traditional Area. It also in the end unriddled and interpreted all the artistic values to members of the community. The chiefs and other structured traditional leaders are installed by going through rigorous phases to gain efficient gratification, validity, fairness and authentication from ancestors, predecessors, traditional leaders and members of the community.

In another spectrum, the chiefs' installation phases outdoors the rich, maintained and admired cultural heritage that have been consistently preserved. Beneath these, the embedded indigenous arts have been unraveled through their sacred and cultural practices, rituals and traditions. These included, appreciation of *bikusidome* with amulets worn by the chiefs and other highly ranked traditional leaders, oral arts such as incantations body art, exhibition of the *dzikle* by the *dziklebiwa*. The slaughtering act by *ogayee* revealed its significance of spirituality, bonding and connectivity with the ancestors. The royal sword which shows craftiness skills was used to carve displays sculpture qualities. The swearing in ignites the commitment the new chief possesses. There was an exhibition of a variety of aesthetic artefacts such as stools, pots, calabash, beads, amulets, libation performances, and musical dance performances. The cultural and sacred practices, and artistic values discovered in the installation practices of the Chiefs of Tsikor clan need to be recognized and promoted by the

prestigious stakeholders in relation to art such as the Museums and Monuments Board, National Commission on Culture, and Centre for National Culture need to beef up their objectives to promote and outdoor the nature of this traditional chief installation of the Avatime traditional area for their heirs, future descendants and to serve the scholarly academic records purposes.

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